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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17127287>**Cytotoxic and Apoptotic Effects of Chloramphenicol on a Canine D-17 Osteosarcoma Cell Line**Gamze Sevri EKREN AŞICI^{1*}¹ Aydın Adnan Menderes University, Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, 09020 Aydın, TürkiyeCorresponding Author Email: gamze.ekren@adu.edu.tr**Article Info**

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Abstract: Osteosarcoma is the most common primary bone tumor in canines current treatment options are limited and often ineffective, necessitating the exploration of alternative therapeutic strategies. Chloramphenicol (CAP), a broad-spectrum antibiotic, has recently gained attention for its potential antitumor properties in various cancer cell lines. This study aimed to evaluate the cytotoxic and apoptotic effects of chloramphenicol on the canine D-17 osteosarcoma cell line to investigate its potential as a novel therapeutic agent. D-17 cells were cultured and treated with varying concentrations of chloramphenicol (ranging from 50 µg/mL to 500 µg/mL) for 24, 48, and 72 hours. Cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay. Apoptosis was evaluated by ELISA using a canine-specific commercial kit for apoptotic markers caspase 3, 8, and 9. The potential effect of chloramphenicol on the colony-forming capacity of cells was evaluated using the crystal violet staining method. Changes in the mineralization ability of the cells were analyzed through the Alizarin Red S staining technique. Additionally, alterations in alkaline phosphatase (ALP) enzyme activity in osteosarcoma cells following chloramphenicol treatment were quantitatively determined using a colorimetric method. Chloramphenicol exhibited a high dose- and time-dependent cytotoxic effect on D-17 cells, with significant reduction in cell viability observed at concentrations ≥ 250 µg/mL. Caspase-3 activity was significantly elevated in treated groups. Chloramphenicol demonstrates significant cytotoxic and pro-apoptotic effects on canine D-17 osteosarcoma cells in vitro. These findings suggest a potential repurposing of this antibiotic as an anticancer agent in canine osteosarcoma, warranting further in vivo studies and clinical evaluation.

Introduction

Osteosarcoma (OSA) is the most common primary bone tumor in dogs, representing approximately 4% of all malignancies and nearly 85% of skeletal neoplasms. The disease is relatively frequent in the canine population, with an estimated annual incidence exceeding 8,000 cases (Curtis et al 2011, Mantovani et al 2016, Millanta et al 2012; Wilson-Robles et al 2019). The prevalence of OSA in dogs remains uncertain, but it is estimated to be 10-50 times more prevalent than in humans (Makielski et al 2019). In dogs, OSA predominantly develops in the metaphyseal regions of long bones, though it can occasionally affect the ribs and cranial bones. The distal radius, proximal humerus, proximal tibia, distal tibia, and distal femur are reported as the most frequently involved sites (Messerschmitt et al 2009). OSA exhibits a high degree of malignancy, characterized by a rapid growth rate and a strong tendency to metastasize (Benassi et al 2007, Evdokiou et al 2003, Fu et al 2011). Approximately 15% of dogs diagnosed with OSA present with clinically detectable disease at the time of initial diagnosis, while over 90% already harbor micrometastases. The tumor predominantly metastasizes to the lungs, and regional lymph node involvement has been reported in approximately 25% of cases (Gill et al 2013, Kirpensteijn et al 2002, Sharili et al 2011).

OSA in dogs exhibits a sex-related predisposition, with the peak incidence in males occurring between 11 and 12 years of age, whereas in females it is more frequently observed between 9 and 10 years of age. Furthermore, the prevalence of OSA is reported to be higher in males compared to females (Fenger et al 2014). In addition to age and sex predispositions, body size and breed represent important risk factors for the development of OSA in dogs. Large and giant breeds show a markedly higher likelihood of developing OSA compared to small breeds. Among them, St. Bernards, Rottweilers, and Scottish Deerhounds exhibit particularly aggressive forms of the disease, likely due to genetic susceptibility. Furthermore, breeds such as Doberman Pinschers, Great Danes, Golden Retrievers, German Shepherds, Collies, Irish Wolfhounds, and Irish Setters demonstrate a higher incidence of OSA. By contrast, limited information is available regarding the risk of osteosarcoma in Greyhounds, and current data remain insufficient to establish a clear association (Kutsal et al 2003, Rosenberger et al 2007, Vascellari et al 2009). Another well-documented risk factor for the development of OSA in dogs is body weight. Several studies have reported that the likelihood of OSA increases proportionally with increasing body mass, indicating that heavier dogs are at significantly greater risk of developing the disease (Fenger et al 2014, Kutsal et al 2003).

The most commonly employed treatment approach is limb amputation of the affected extremity. When this surgical intervention is followed by adjuvant chemotherapy, both survival time and quality of life of the patient can be significantly improved (Szewczyk et al 2015). In cases where only surgical intervention is performed, the average survival time ranges between 4 and 6 months, whereas the addition of chemotherapy can extend this period to 10–12 months, and in some cases, up to 2 years (Mauldin et al 1988). Radiotherapy is generally preferred for the palliative management of pain (Mayer and Grier 2006, Poon et al 2020). Due to the aggressive nature of osteosarcoma and the high risk of early metastasis, early diagnosis is of great importance. In the management of this disease in canines, a multidisciplinary approach is required both to control the tumor and to preserve the quality of life (Poon et al 2020, Ringdahl-Mayland et al 2022).

Chloramphenicol (CAP) is a broad-spectrum antibiotic effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with established applications in human and veterinary medicine (Hutchings et al 2019, Ventola 2015). It was first isolated in 1947 from the bacterium *Streptomyces venezuelae* and was later produced synthetically (Liu et al 2024). CAP acts by binding to the 50S ribosomal subunit, thereby inhibiting peptidyl transferase and halting

bacterial protein synthesis. Due to structural similarities between prokaryotic ribosomes and mammalian mitochondria, mitochondrial protein synthesis may also be affected (Tian et al 2016).

It is effective against a wide range of microbial infections, including cholera, typhoid, rickettsial diseases, meningitis, and certain infections of the central nervous system (Oong and Tadi 2023). However, numerous case reports are indicating that bone marrow suppression leads to aplastic anemia in humans and causes hematological disorders such as leukemia (Patel et al 2019, Yuan and Shi 2008). Moreover, due to serious adverse effects in humans, such as esophagitis, gray baby syndrome, and optic neuritis, the systemic use of chloramphenicol has been discontinued in developed countries (Hsu et al 2019, Oong and Tadi 2023). In 1997, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) banned the use of chloramphenicol in food-producing animals. However, it continues to be used in cats, dogs, and horses for the treatment of both systemic and localized infections (Patel et al 2019, Oong and Tadi 2023).

Although chloramphenicol is primarily known as a broad-spectrum antibiotic used for the treatment of bacterial infections, recent studies have suggested that this molecule may also possess anticancer potential. Its anticancer effect is primarily attributed to the inhibition of intracellular mitochondrial protein synthesis (Hsu et al 2019, Tian et al 2016).

Information obtained from human medicine is frequently used when using chemotherapeutic agents in veterinary medicine. Due to differences in pharmacokinetic parameters and the sensitivity of tumor cells to cancer therapeutic compounds, the direct application of chemotherapeutic protocols from human medicine is controversial. Differences between different types of tumors and the suitability of certain canine cancers as therapeutic models for human cancer and vice versa are also described (Mueller et al 2007, Vail and MacEwen 2000). Therefore, demonstrating that chloramphenicol, which has been shown to exert anticancer effects in other cancer types, also possesses anticancer activity in dogs, particularly in OSA, is of significant importance.

Materials and Methods

Culturing D-17 (CCL-183) Canine OSA Cell Line

The canine osteosarcoma cell line D-17 (CCL-183; ATCC, Manassas, VA) was cultured in Eagle's Minimum Essential Medium (Sigma, M4655) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Sigma, F0804), 0.1% penicillin/streptomycin (10,000 U/mL; Gibco), 1% non-essential amino acids (Sigma, M7145), and 0.11 g/L sodium pyruvate. Cells were maintained at 37 °C in a humidified incubator containing 5% CO₂ and passages 7–12 were used for all experiments.

The Effect of CAP on Cell Viability

D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^3 cells per well and incubated for 24 h to allow adherence. After attachment, cells were treated with CAP (Sigma Aldrich, C3175 Chloramphenicol-Water Soluble) at concentrations ranging from 50 to 500 µg/ml and incubated at 37 °C for 24, 48, or 72 h. At the end of each incubation period, the CAP-containing medium was replaced with 100 µL of fresh medium supplemented with MTT solutions (SERVA-298-93-1, Germany). Cells were then incubated for an additional 4 h under standard culture conditions (37 °C, 5% CO₂, 95% humidity), and absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (Thermo Scientific Multiskan GO, Finland). All treatments were performed in quadruplicate, and each experiment was independently repeated three times. Cell viability was expressed as a percentage relative to untreated controls, and IC₅₀ values were calculated using GraphPad Prism 9.3 software (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA).

Determination of Viability by Crystal Violet Staining

D-17 cells were seeded in 24-well plates at a density of 1×10^4 cells per well and allowed to adhere for 24 h. Following treatment with CAP (50 µg/mL, 100 µg/mL, 150 µg/mL, 200 µg/mL, 250 µg/mL, 300 µg/mL, 400 µg/mL and 500 µg/mL) for 48 or 72 h, cells were gently washed with PBS and fixed in 10% formaldehyde at room temperature for 10 min. Subsequently, a 0.5% crystal violet solution prepared in methanol was added to each well and incubated for 15 min. Excess dye was removed, and plates were imaged. Colony formation was evaluated by comparing the stained cell colonies between treatment groups (Ekren-Aşıcı and Kırıl, 2024).

Effect of CAP on Mineralization

Alizarin Red S staining was used to assess the effect of CAP on mineralization, following the protocol described by Gregory et al. (2004). D-17 cells were seeded in 24-well plates at a density of 1×10^4 cells per well and allowed to attach for 24 h. Cells were subsequently treated with varying concentrations of CAP (at concentrations ranging from 50 to 500 µg/mL), alongside control and negative control groups, and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ for 48 or 72 hours. After treatment, cells were fixed with 10% formaldehyde for 10 min at room temperature, rinsed with PBS, and subsequently stained with 0.04 M Alizarin Red S for 30 min on a plate shaker. Excess dye was removed by washing with PBS, and images of the stained cultures were captured for evaluation.

Effect of CAP on Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) Activity

D-17 cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^4 cells per well in 6-well plates and treated with varying concentrations of CAP (ranging from 50 to 500 µg/mL). After 48 and 72 hours, the medium was collected individually in Eppendorf tubes to determine the level of ALP released. The cells were harvested using trypsin-EDTA, washed with PBS and lysed in ice-cold RIPA buffer (Santa Cruz Biotechnology). The lysates were then centrifuged at 1,000 g for 15 minutes at 4 °C after which the resulting supernatant was collected for ALP activity measurement as described by Nash et al. (2015). Enzyme activity was determined by measuring the absorbance of p-nitrophenol produced from the hydrolysis of p-nitrophenylphosphate, according to the method described by Tietz, (1983) at 405 nm. Protein concentrations were quantified using a BCA protein assay kit (Biovision, USA) and ALP activity was normalised to total protein content.

Assessment of apoptosis through measurement of caspase 3, caspase 8, and caspase 9 activities using ELISA.

D-17 cells were incubated with CAP at concentrations of 150, 225, and 500 µg/mL for 48 and 72 hours. After treatment, 5×10^6 cells were harvested and counted. Subsequently, the cells were lysed using RIPA buffer and centrifuged at $10,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4 °C. The supernatants were collected, and the levels of caspase-3, -8, and -9 were measured using canine-specific ELISA kits (FineTest, China) designed for cell culture applications. All assays were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical analysis

GraphPad Prism v9.3 (GraphPad Software; La Jolla, CA, USA) and SPSS for Windows Ver. 22.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL., USA) package programs were used. The normality of the variables was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. For descriptive analyses, mean and standard deviation values were calculated for both normally and non-normally distributed variables. The conformity of all measured variables to a normal distribution, considering both continuous and categorical data, was further examined visually using histograms and

probability plots, and analytically using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests. Descriptive statistics are presented as mean ± standard error values.

The null hypothesis (H_0) of the study stated that the application of the broad-spectrum antibiotic chloramphenicol at different doses to the canine osteosarcoma cell line would not result in significant differences in antiproliferative and anticancer effects. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) proposed that chloramphenicol treatment at varying doses would produce significant differences in these effects. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to evaluate whether statistically significant differences existed between the means of treated and untreated groups. Homogeneity of variances was verified using Levene’s test. In cases where ANOVA indicated significant differences among groups, Tukey’s post-hoc test was applied. A P-value of less than 0.05 was considered indicative of statistical significance.

Results

The effects of different concentrations of CAP (ranging from 50 µg/mL to 500 µg/mL) on the viability of D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells were evaluated using the MTT assay after exposure for 24, 48, and 72 hours. Cell viability at each concentration was calculated as a percentage relative to the control group (Figure 1 a–c). Subsequently, a dose–response curve was generated using GraphPad Prism 9.3 software (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA) (Figure 2 a–c). The IC_{50} value of CAP treatment on the D-17 cell line at 24 hours could not be determined, as less than 50% inhibition was observed compared with the control group at the end of incubation. In contrast, the IC_{50} values of CAP at 48 and 72 hours were calculated as 272.98 ± 5.06 µM and 224 ± 2.98 µM, respectively.

Figure 1. Effect of CAP on the viability of D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells following 24 h (a), 48 h (b), and 72 h (c) treatments.

Cells were treated with increasing concentrations of CAP (50–500 µg/mL), and cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay. Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) of independent experiments. Cell viability is expressed as a percentage relative to the untreated control group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post hoc test. ns: not significant, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Figure 2. Dose–response relationship of CAP on D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells

CAP: Chloramphenicol

After 24 hours of exposure of D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells to CAP, cell viability at concentrations of 50, 100, and 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ did not show statistically significant changes compared with the control group ($p>0.05$); however, a statistically significant increase was observed at the 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ dose ($p<0.05$). Although slight decreases in cell viability were observed at intermediate concentrations of 200 and 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, these differences were not statistically significant. However, at concentrations of 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and above, cell viability was markedly reduced, with statistically significant differences compared to the control group ($p<0.001$) (Figure 1a). After 48 hours of CAP exposure, D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells exhibited a dose-dependent response in cell viability (Figure 1b). Notably, cell viability was significantly reduced at concentrations of 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and above, with the most pronounced cytotoxic effects observed at 400 and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p<0.001$). After 72 hours of CAP treatment, a pronounced dose-dependent decrease in cell viability was observed in D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells (Şekil 1c). Significant reductions in cell viability began to appear at the 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ dose, becoming statistically significant at 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p<0.01$). At concentrations of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and above, cell viability was markedly lower compared to the control group, and these differences were statistically significant ($p<0.001$). The data obtained support that CAP exerts a strong cytotoxic effect on D-17 cells in a dose- and time-dependent manner.

Cell viability by crystal violet staining

Treatment of D-17 cells with CAP resulted in a concentration-dependent decrease in both viability and clonogenic potential (Figure 3). The first clearly observable cytotoxic response occurred at 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, whereas lower concentrations induced only minor reductions compared to control. In contrast, significant inhibition of colony formation and cell survival was detected 300–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ at CAP concentrations, confirming a potent cytotoxic effect at these levels.

Figure 3. The effect of CAP on the viability of D-17 osteosarcoma cells after 48 and 72 hours of incubation.

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Effect of CAP on mineralization

Mineralization responses in D-17 cells were found to be influenced by both CAP concentration and incubation duration. Cells treated with lower CAP doses (50–250 µg/mL) exhibited enhanced mineral capacity compared to controls at both 48 and 72 hours. Conversely, exposure to higher CAP concentrations (250–500 µg/mL) significantly suppressed mineral formation (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Time-Dependent Effects of CAP on Mineralization in D-17 Osteosarcoma Cells (48 h and 72 h)

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Changes in ALP Activity Following CAP Exposure in Canine Osteosarcoma Cell Line (D-17)

The reduction in extracellular ALP activity of D-17 cells treated with various doses of CAP was not statistically significant after 48 and 72 hours of incubation ($p > 0.05$) (Figures. 5 a-b). In contrast, intracellular ALP activity in D-17 cells exposed to all CAP doses (50–500 µg/mL) was significantly reduced in a dose-dependent manner compared with the control group ($p < 0.001$). (Figures. 6 a–b)

Figure 5. Extracellular ALP activity alterations in D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells following 48-hours (a) and 72-hours (b) exposure to varying concentrations of CAP. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. ns: not significant, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Figure 6. Intracellular ALP activity alterations in D-17 canine osteosarcoma cells following 48-hours (a) and 72-hours (b) exposure to varying concentrations of CAP. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post hoc test. ns: not significant, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Alterations in caspase 3, caspase 8, and caspase 9 levels in D-17 cells following CAP treatment.

To evaluate apoptotic parameters, cells were exposed to CAP at concentrations of 150, 225, and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 48 and 72 hours, selected based on the IC_{50} value. These concentrations correspond to: 225 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as the IC_{50} dose, 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as a sub- IC_{50} dose showing antiproliferative activity, and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as an overdose above the IC_{50} level.

After 48 hours of incubation, no statistically significant difference was observed between the control and CAP-treated groups ($p > 0.05$). In the 72-hour samples, however, a significant increase was detected in the group treated with 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ CAP compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). This difference became even more pronounced at CAP doses of 225 and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Figure 7 a). These findings indicate that the apoptotic effect of CAP occurs through caspase-8 in a manner dependent on both exposure time and dose.

Measurements in D-17 cells demonstrated that CAP treatment increased caspase-9 levels in a dose- and time-dependent manner. After 48 hours of incubation, no significant difference was observed in the 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ CAP group compared with the control, whereas a marked elevation was detected at 225 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p < 0.01$) and the highest increase occurred at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p < 0.001$). At 72 hours, the 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ group showed a slight but statistically significant rise ($p < 0.05$). Significant increases persisted at 225 and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p < 0.001$); however, a slight decline was noted at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ compared with the 48-hour value (Figure 7 b). These findings suggest that CAP markedly elevates caspase-9 activity at higher doses, particularly at earlier time points, indicating activation of the intrinsic (mitochondrial) apoptotic pathway.

The findings indicate that CAP treatment significantly increases caspase-3 levels in D-17 cells in both a time- and dose-dependent manner. After 48 hours of incubation, no statistically significant difference was detected in the 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ CAP group compared with the control, whereas a slight but significant elevation was observed in the 225 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ group ($p < 0.05$). At 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, a clear and statistically significant rise in caspase-3 levels was also recorded at 48 hours ($p < 0.05$). After 72 hours of exposure, the effects became more pronounced: the change in the 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ group remained limited, while the 225 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ group showed a marked and

highly significant increase ($p < 0.001$), and the 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ group exhibited the highest caspase-3 level ($p < 0.001$). These results demonstrate that CAP elevates caspase-3 activity in D-17 cells in a dose- and time-dependent manner, strongly triggering the execution phase of apoptosis.

Figure 7. Graphs showing changes in caspase-3 and caspase-9 levels in response to different doses of CAP caspase 8 (a), caspase 9 (b) caspase 3 (c). Means labeled with different letters indicate statistically significant differences. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. ns: not significant, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

CAP: Chloramphenicol

Discussion

Cancer is known as a major health problem globally (Bilici et al., 2025). It is more common in pets at older ages. This process coincides with the times when the pet and the owner relationship is the strongest. The patient owner prefers to take all necessary interventions for this pet's health. During this time, he expects a satisfactory result from all his expenses (Biller et al., 2016). Therefore, in the cancer treatments of pets, it should be effective and anti-metastatic as well as palliative treatment.

The skeletal system is a common site of neoplasia in dogs and cats. Osteosarcoma is the most common type of primary bone malignancy; a non-hemopoietic malignant tumour of the skeletal system derived from primitive mesenchymal cells, and is particularly malignant in cats and dogs (Dittmer and Pemberton, 2021; George and Mani, 2011). OSA is an aggressive metastatic cancer type that generally tends to metastasize to the lung (Szewczyk et al., 2015). Among the treatment options, the most effective is usually the amputation of the affected

extremity. However, this treatment option is not preferred by patient owners. Although the combination of chemotherapy and chemotherapy with surgical methods has significantly increased the survival time in osteosarcoma, deaths occur due to the side effects of chemotherapy. The cytotoxic effects of chemotherapy on normal tissues are a major disadvantage in the treatment of dogs with OSA, as in any cancer treatment. In addition, the use of anticancer drugs causes serious problems such as the emergence of drug-resistant phenotypes and the emergence of second malignancies. Therefore, great efforts have been made to identify alternative approaches to current chemotherapy (Alleva et al., 2006; Anninga et al., 2011; Fenger et al., 2014). In addition, there is still no worldwide consensus on a standard chemotherapy approach.

Chloramphenicol, a classical antibiotic known to inhibit mitochondrial protein synthesis in mammals, has long been used due to its low cost and ease of synthesis (Tian et al., 2016). Historically, it was employed in the treatment of typhoid, anaerobic infections, meningitis, brain abscesses, and rickettsial infections; however, its clinical application became limited because of adverse effects. In recent years, various studies have aimed to minimize these side effects. Due to rising rates of drug resistance, there is an immediate need for innovative antibiotics and anticancer medicines (Bilici and Akkoç, 2025). With the growing interest in the anticancer potential of antibiotics, chloramphenicol has also been investigated for its effects on cancer cells. Previous studies have demonstrated that chloramphenicol can arrest the cell cycle, induce apoptosis, and suppress DNA synthesis, particularly in leukemia, glioblastoma, and several solid tumor cell lines (Tian et al., 2016; Hsu et al., 2019; Yuan and Shi, 2008). Despite these findings, no studies have yet reported on the anticancer effects of chloramphenicol in canine osteosarcoma, highlighting a gap in the current literature and a potential area for further investigation.

In our study, both crystal violet and MTT assay results demonstrated that CAP exerts an antiproliferative effect on canine OSA cell lines. Similarly, Tian et al. (2016) demonstrated that chloramphenicol (CAP) exerts a strong cytotoxic effect on multiple myeloma (MM) cells in a dose- and time-dependent manner. Using colorimetric and clonogenic assays, they reported that CAP inhibited the proliferation of myeloma cells at concentrations below 50 µg/mL, while at concentrations under 25 µg/mL, cell growth was markedly suppressed.

It has been shown that human osteosarcoma (OSA) cell lines (MG-63, Saos-2, and U-2) (Farley et al., 1989; Pautke et al., 2004), mouse OSA cell lines (Ali et al., 1993), and canine OSA cell lines (Ekren-Aşıcı and Kırıl, 2024) produce high levels of ALP. Progression, spread, or metastasis of OSA is thought to increase osteolysis and ALP levels. Elevated ALP has been associated with OSA malignancy and poor treatment outcomes (Ren et al., 2015). Our results indicate that, based on ALP activity assays and alizarin red staining, CAP treatment reduces intracellular ALP levels in a dose- and time-dependent manner and, in parallel, decreases calcium-binding capacity. These findings suggest that CAP may be a potential therapeutic agent for the treatment of OSA.

Analysis of caspase assays revealed that chloramphenicol (CAP) induced a clear, dose- and time-dependent increase in caspase-3 levels in the OSA cell line. No significant change in caspase-8 levels was observed during the first 48 hours; however, a slight elevation was detected at 72 hours. In contrast, caspase-9 levels showed a marked increase dependent on both dose and exposure time. In summary, chloramphenicol particularly elevated caspase-9 and caspase-3 levels, thereby contributing to the induction of apoptotic processes in the cells. In their study, Tian et al. (2016) reported that chloramphenicol (CAP) inhibits mitochondrial protein synthesis and proliferation in multiple myeloma (MM) cells. Flow cytometry and Western blot analyses demonstrated that CAP, at concentrations below 50 µg/mL, induces

apoptosis, increases levels of cytochrome c, cleaved caspase-9, and cleaved caspase-3, and activates the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway. Furthermore, CAP has been shown to induce autophagy and suppress HIF-1 α signaling in non-small cell lung cancer cells (Hsu et al., 2019), as well as to affect T-cell differentiation and apoptosis in leukemia models both in vitro and in vivo (Yuan and Shi, 2008), thereby supporting these findings. In conclusion, although the data on the anticancer effects of chloramphenicol in the canine OSA cell line are promising, these studies remain at the experimental stage, and further research is needed before clinical application.

Conclusion

In recent years, studies have suggested that chloramphenicol may exhibit antitumor effects in certain cancer cell types. These effects vary depending on cell type, dose, exposure duration, and experimental conditions. However, no specific studies have investigated the effects of chloramphenicol on canine osteosarcoma (OSA) cells or tumors. The novelty of our study lies in its direct evaluation of chloramphenicol's effects on canine OSA cell lines in terms of antiproliferative activity and apoptotic mechanisms. No data, studies, or case reports currently exist in the literature; therefore, the findings from this study provide a unique contribution to understanding chloramphenicol's effects on canine OSA and offer a novel perspective for existing treatment protocols.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

Availability of Data and Materials

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Ethical Statement

No ethical approval was required, as this study required no animal experiments.

Author Contributions

Motivation/Concept: GSEA; Design: GSEA, FK; Control/Supervision: GSEA, FK; Data Collection and Processing: GSEA, FK; Analysis and Interpretation: GSEA; Literature Review: GSEA, FK; Writing the Article: GSEA; Critical Review: GSEA, FK

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